

REACTIONS OF HYPONITRITES. PART I. THE ACTION OF CHARCOAL ON SODIUM NITRITE ETC.

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Hyponitrites are formed by the action of charcoal on alkali nitrites. They, however, undergo double decomposition with the carbon dioxide formed in the reaction producing the alkali carbonate and nitrous oxide.

Sodium hyponitrite decomposes at 334-36° producing sodium oxide, nitrite and nitrate and liberating nitrogen. It appears likely that oxide and nitrite are the primary products and nitrate is the secondary product formed by auto-oxidation of the nitrite. This view receives support from the products of action of charcoal on sodium nitrite and hyponitrite.

Sodium hyponitrite is extraordinarily sensitive to carbon dioxide, fixing the latter becoming itself changed into the carbonate and setting nitrous oxide free. The sensitiveness is so unusual that it removes carbon dioxide even from air where it is present only to a small extent.

While studying the action of charcoal on potassium nitrite (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 267) the author detected the presence of a small amount of nitrous oxide in the slow reaction. The observation could not be substantiated as the reaction between potassium nitrite and charcoal was always violent. Interest about the observation developed, however, as this indicated the possibility of a further side reaction leading to the formation of potassium hyponitrite, as formation of nitrous oxide from the action of charcoal on other oxides of nitrogen is precluded (Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2661). As sodium nitrite melts at a comparatively low temperature (about 335°) it was thought that this substance might react with charcoal at a lower temperature and the hyponitrite, if produced, might be detected with comparative ease since sodium hyponitrite is known to decompose above 300° (Divers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, **61**, 97). Experiments have therefore been performed to substantiate the formation of nitrous oxide in the interaction and to trace its origin.

Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction started at about 300°, slowly gathered speed and became measurable at 325°. The reaction rate increased with increasing temperature and became violent at 360-65°. After the violence the reaction practically ceased. The reaction had the characteristics of a chain reaction as in the case of potassium nitrate and charcoal, starting slowly and developing speed with time at a constant temperature. An examination of the gaseous products revealed the presence of about 50 % nitrous oxide but the examination of the residue by the usual test did not indicate any hyponitrite therein.

In the present work results of experiments (i) at different temperature and (ii) with different proportions of the reactants are described. The formation of sodium hyponitrite, as an intermediate unstable product, is established by devising a method of detecting the substance based on the observation of Partington and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2071). The thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite, pure and in presence of charcoal, is studied and the action of carbon dioxide on sodium hyponitrite investigated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Materials.—Merck's extra pure sodium nitrite was recrystallised from alcohol-water and dried. Pure charcoal was prepared from cane sugar by a combination of the methods

of Shah (*loc. cit.*) and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 843). The charcoal used in these experiments left 0.07 % ash on incineration.

Apparatus and Procedure.—A carefully weighed quantity of the reactants was heated electrically in a vacuum at the bottom of a 1 foot vertical column sealed on to the Sprengel pump with a tap in between. No KOH trap was necessary as the gas produced contained very little nitrogen tetroxide. The apparatus, tested for leaks, was evacuated by Hyvac followed by Sprengel for fifteen minutes. As the charcoal gave out adsorbed gas on commencing to heat, the apparatus was once again evacuated at 250°.

Analysis.—The gas showed nitrous oxide, nitrogen, carbon dioxide and traces of carbon monoxide and nitric oxide. These were estimated by the standard methods: nitrous oxide was absorbed out in cold alcohol saturated with nitric oxide and carbon monoxide in a nitrogen atmosphere after previously absorbing carbon dioxide in strong KOH saturated with nitrous oxide. All volumes stated are at N.T.P.

The solid residue showed no nitrate (diphenylamine test). It contained carbonate, nitrite, and hyponitrite (with probably some carbide). The hyponitrite, present only in very small amounts, was detected thus: the residue after pumping off the gas was allowed to cool to room temperature under the prevailing vacuum and about 1 c.c. water added cautiously by turning the tap T (Fig. 1). Gas was liberated and this was collected dry, by passing over a layer of potassium carbonate and phosphorus pentoxide. The analysis of this gas

FIG. 1.

showed nitrous oxide and nitrogen. Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) observed that sodium hyponitrite produced a mixture of nitrous oxide and nitrogen on treatment with water in a vacuum. The very small amount of hyponitrite present had, probably, its colour masked in the thick precipitate due to the carbonate and the nitrite simultaneously present (with silver nitrate).

The nitrite was determined with permanganate, adding excess tetroxalate and titrating the tetroxalate excess: carbonate by weak HCl.

Effect of Temperature.—The results of experiments with sodium nitrite and 20 % (on the weight of nitrite) charcoal at different temperatures are given in Table I. The reaction was controllable up to 350°, but was violent in 5 to 6 minutes at 360° and in 3 to 4 minutes at 370°.

TABLE I
Action of charcoal on sodium nitrite at different temperatures.

Temp.	NaNO ₂	Gas total.	% Composition of gases				Residue		
			N ₂ .	N ₂ O.	CO ₂ .	CO.	NO.	NaNO ₂ .	Na ₂ CO ₃
325°	0.1743 g.	23.5	31.5	54.9	11.5	0.6	0.9	0.071	0.0867
340	0.1806	32.95	34.3	51.5	12.4	1.0	0.6	—	—
350	0.1803	27.5	35.2	50.0	12.0	1.5	0.7	0.0614	0.0986
360	0.1442	30.85	40.6	31.1	17.2	5.7	5.6	0.0154	0.1049
370	0.1476	26.7	45.7	25.5	17.0	6.2	6.0	0.0441	0.0895

The results show that (i) so long as the reaction is under control (a) the proportions of nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide and nitrogen are practically the same; nitrous oxide slightly diminishing and the latter two slightly increasing with rising temperature; (b) the proportions of nitric oxide and carbon monoxide are small; (ii) in the violent reaction, the proportion of nitrogen increases and that of nitrous oxide diminishes, the changes being the greater, the earlier the violence setting in. The proportions of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and nitric oxide increase in the violent reaction, the observation being just the same as in the case of charcoal and potassium nitrite (*loc. cit.*).

As reduction in the proportion of nitrous oxide in the violent reaction tends towards the absence or abatement of the corresponding reaction in the violent stage and would, in this respect, be in complete analogy with the potassium nitrite and charcoal results, experiments were conducted by separating the gaseous products of the violent reaction. As the effect of temperature is only slight the slow reaction was begun at 340° and the evolved gas continuously pumped off and the temperature gradually raised till (after 65 min.) the violence set in (at only 355°) when the tap between the heating column and the pump was turned off and the gas on the pump side collected along with the former (a). The tap was next opened and the remaining gas collected separately (b). As the reaction immediately before violence was fairly rapid, all the gas formed before the violence could not be collected in (a) so that (b) does contain some of (a). Under (c) is given the results of another experiment with the same amounts of the reactants, the gas being allowed to accumulate in the system till (after 106 min.) the reaction ceased altogether. The results of these experiments are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Gas evolved under continuous pumping (a) before, (b) during the violent reaction and (c) when allowed to accumulate in the system.

	NaNO ₂	Gas (total)	Percentage composition of gas					Residue	
			N ₂	N ₂ O	CO ₂	CO	NO	NaNO ₂	Na ₂ CO ₃
(a)	0·3753 g.	49·8	51·8	32·6	13·4	1·2	1·6	—	—
(b)		23·5	63·8	8·5	17·0	6·9	4·8	—	—
(c)	0·3748	77·5	52·8	31·4	13·8	0·9	1·0	0·0028g.	0·3020g.

The results show in addition to the normal features of Table I that (i) there is a considerable difference in the proportions of nitrous oxide and nitrogen in (a) and (b), the former being very small in the violent reaction; (ii) there is little difference in the nature of gaseous products whether the gas is continuously pumped off or allowed to accumulate in the system during the reaction except that in the latter case the reaction is slower; this shows that the reactions all occur in the solid (or molten) phase and not in the gaseous phase; (iii) the effect of increase in mass of the reactants is (*cf.* Table I) to reduce the production of nitrous oxide probably by a rise in local temperature (the reactions are exothermic) which hinder the production of hyponitrite. With potassium nitrite and charcoal (*loc. cit.*) where the slow reaction occurred at about 400°, very little nitrous oxide was detected.

Effect of Mass of Charcoal.—Effect of mass of charcoal on the production of nitrous oxide was next studied by carrying out the reaction at 340° with different proportions of

charcoal. The reactions were stopped when about 10 c.c. of gas were collected. This was immaterial as will be seen by comparing Table I or II and III since the composition of the gas was practically uniform whether the extent of the reaction was small or large. These results are given in Table III and show that the effect of increasing the proportion of charcoal is similar to a rise in temperature.

TABLE III

Effect of mass of charcoal at 340°.

Charcoal.	NaNO ₂ .	Gas (total).	Percentage composition of gas				
			N ₂ .	N ₂ O.	CO ₂ .	CO.	NO.
5%	0.1719 g.	4.3	41.9	46.5	9.3	2.2	1.0
20	0.1798	8.8	37.5	49.6	11.5	1.0	1.0
60	0.1800	8.4	42.5	42.0	11.0	2.5	2.0

The residue of the 60% experiment, when cold, was treated with water in order to test for hyponitrite in the manner stated before. The evolved gas was collected and examined. As the result showed the presence of nitrous oxide, experiments were performed with 10% charcoal at lower temperature (330-35°) so as to facilitate the production of hyponitrite. Two experiments were performed—one short, in which heating was done till only about 10 c.c. gas were produced and the other long where about five times as much gas was formed. The gas was removed by Hyvac and Sprengel, the residue allowed to cool to room temperature in the vacuum and then treated with water. The composition of the gas thus obtained is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Gas evolved on water treatment of the cold residues in vacuo.

NaNO ₂ .	Charcoal.	Gas (total).	% Composition of the gas	
			N ₂ O.	N ₂ (with some combustible gas).
0.1800 g.	60% (short)	1.35	0.4	0.95
0.1803	10 (short)	1.85	1.2	0.65
0.1795	10 (long)	5.4	3.5	1.9

The results justify the belief that hyponitrite is produced in the reaction. Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) have shown that gas of some such composition as this is evolved when sodium hyponitrite is treated under vacuum with water. The gas, unabsorbed in alcohol, caught fire when the tube containing it was held slanting, top up, near a spirit lamp flame producing a blue flame which descended steadily but swiftly down the length of the tube occupied by the gas. The gas may not be containing hydrogen for, on admixture with air, it did not explode. It might be some hydrocarbon, mixed with nitrogen, produced by the action of water on some traces of carbide present in the residue.

Having thus proved that hyponitrite was produced in the reaction the question next was to explain as to how nitrous oxide was formed from the hyponitrite. The thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite has been studied by several workers and though reference books (Mellor) show that nitrous oxide is produced by the thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite, the work

of Divers (*loc. cit.*), Ray and Ganguli (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1396) and Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) showed that the substance may not be produced from the hyponitrite by thermal decomposition. These workers have shown that nitrous oxide is one of the components of the gas produced by the thermal decomposition of cupric, alkaline earth, lead, zinc, mercury but not silver and sodium hyponitrites. Berthelot and Petit (*Compt. rend.*, 1889, **109**, 92) showed from a consideration of the heats of formation of hyponitrous acid in aqueous solution and of nitrous oxide that it was possible for sodium hyponitrite to decompose into nitrous oxide and sodium oxide. It was therefore thought worthwhile to carry out a few experiments on heating sodium hyponitrite.

Thermal Decomposition of Sodium Hyponitrite.—Pure sodium hyponitrite was prepared by the Diver's (*loc. cit.*) method (modified) to be described in Part II. It was examined for purity: (1) 0.0237 g. anhydrous substance gave 0.0260 g. NaCl; (2) 0.0298 g. anhydrous substance gave 0.0796 g. AgCl; (3) the substance contained no carbonate. (Found: Na, 43.1; N₂O₂, 55.8%; Na₂N₂O₂ requires Na, 43.4 and N₂O₂, 56.6%). Weighed quantities of the salt were heated in the same apparatus and in the same way as described before. As the reported temperature of the thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite is different according to different workers (Divers, above 300°; Partington and Shah, 260-65°) this was also determined. Above 250° temperature of the furnace was allowed to rise only very slowly, 10° in 15 minutes. The substance showed first signs of decomposition (fluctuation of mercury in the Sprengel pump) at 334-36° and decomposed suddenly in about 2 minutes thereafter. During the first two minutes the decomposition was but gradual. After the suddenness the reaction practically ceased. The gas was nitrogen (with only a trace of nitric oxide). The glass of the apparatus was corroded. The residue was yellow when cool and dissolved in water with hissing and effervescence. The results of these experiments are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite.

Expt No.	Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ .	Gas (N ₂) N.T.P.	Residue		3Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ = 2Na ₂ O + 2N ₂ + 2NaNO ₂ demands		
			Na ₂ O.	NaNO ₂ .	N ₂ (N.T.P.).	Na ₂ O.	NaNO ₂ .
1	24.9 mg.	3.6 c.c.	9.9 mg.	9.0 mg.	3.5 c.c.	9.7 mg.	10.8 mg.
2	30.2	5.05	12.37	9.69	4.3	11.77	13.1
3	29.8	4.8	—	9.42	4.2	11.62	12.93
4	52.5	9.05	20.2	20.98	7.8	20.5	22.76
5	42.0	7.2	17.6	12.5	5.9	16.38	18.22

Divers (*loc. cit.*) and Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) considered the equation,

to represent the decomposition. They did not give any analytical results in support of their statement. The above results show that the reaction is not so simple. The equation represents, most probably, the primary stage in the decomposition soon followed, under the prevailing conditions, by auto-oxidation of the nitrite. The latter reaction would reduce the amount of nitrite and increase the amounts of oxide and nitrogen in accordance with the above results. In all the above residues the presence of nitrate noticed also by Divers (*loc. cit.*) was distinct (diphenylamine test) and further a trace of nitric oxide was always present in the gas and

all this was to be expected if a part of the sodium nitrite underwent thermal decomposition (Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 107; Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 11, iii, 70).

The action of charcoal on sodium nitrite, studied in order to see if nitrous oxide was produced in the reaction, also confirmed the above view regarding the thermal decomposition of sodium hyponitrite. Using 50 mg. of the salt and 10 mg. of charcoal the reaction was performed in the same apparatus. It occurred at 340-42° and was also sudden. The volume of gas given off was 8.9 c.c. at N.T.P. of which less than 0.1 c.c. was carbon dioxide and the rest was nitrogen with a trace of nitric oxide. The glass tube was little corroded in this reaction. The residue contained Na_2CO_3 , 0.0238 g., Na_2O , 0.00914 g. and NaNO_2 , 0.00374 g. The reaction products were thus the same as with sodium nitrite (Tables I, II and III) except that here there was no nitrous oxide and no free carbon dioxide. The existence, in the residue of such a large proportion of carbonate shows that carbon dioxide was produced in the reaction, i.e., sodium nitrite had decomposed.

Having thus been baffled in tracing the cause of production of nitrous oxide the production of the gas could not be attributed to some sort of interaction between charcoal and oxides of nitrogen under the experimental conditions. The isosterism of nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide and the possibility that the latter might displace the former from sodium hyponitrite seemed to be more plausible in this case. Literature was not of much help. Kirschner (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 16, 424) noted that barium hyponitrite was decomposed by carbon dioxide and Divers (*loc. cit.*) found calcium hyponitrite stable to it. Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) stated that the alkaline earth salts were all stable in air or carbon dioxide but that sodium hyponitrite, when left exposed to air, did not give the characteristic canary yellow precipitate with silver nitrate after a fortnight. They did not, however, trace the cause of such a behaviour. The author investigated the behaviour and was surprised to find the extraordinary case with which carbon dioxide, streamed in a vacuum over sodium hyponitrite, displaced most of the nitrous oxide of the latter at room temperature in a couple of minutes. The residue was sodium carbonate requiring twice the volume of a standard strong acid with methyl orange as with phenolphthalein.

Action of Carbon Dioxide on Sodium Hyponitrite.—The apparatus used is shown in Fig. 2.

A weighed quantity of the substance was kept at **S** near a padding of glass wool in a tube the ends of which were connected by ground glass joints to a 3-way tap **X** on one side and the drying tube **D** on the other. The tube **D** was sealed on to **A** containing sodium bicarbonate to produce carbon dioxide. The tap **X** lead to Sprengel through an internal seal and a bulb **K** containing strong KOH. The empty space **BB** allowed the solution in **K** to rise when required in making adjustments and **T** allowed air to be admitted at the end of experiment and facilitated glass blowing (removing the cock and plugging the ends). The KOH solution used was previously saturated with nitrous oxide and kept in vacuum for a day while testing for leak in the

apparatus. Bubble formation or rise of solution in **K** indicated leak and whenever a leak was found, the substance **S** was removed and replaced by a fresh one. The results of these experiments are given in Table VI. In experiment (i) temperature of the furnace was raised, after the liberation of gas in the cold ceased, to 350° and a little more gas thus collected in the pump. The experiment (ii) was done only in the cold. Practically all the gas was absorbed out in cold alcohol on standing. The unabsorbed gas in experiment (i) was evidently nitrogen produced during the heating stage. The residue was sodium carbonate mixed with a little nitrite in (i) and hyponitrite in (ii). Whenever free hyponitrite was present, together with sodium carbonate in the residue the titration reading with methyl orange was a little over two times that with phenolphthalein.

TABLE VI

Streaming of carbon dioxide over sodium hyponitrite in vacuum

No.	Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ .	Vol. of gas given off.	Composition of gas		Na ₂ CO ₃ formed.
			N ₂ O.	N ₂	
(i)	30 mg.	6.3 c.c.	5.6	0.7	28.1 mg.
(ii)	57	11.34	11.3	0.0	54.3

The great sensitivity of sodium hyponitrite to carbon dioxide is exemplary and this renders the preparation and preservation of the substance and also its handling extremely difficult. This will be described in Part II but it may be stated here that practically the whole of the substance becomes spoiled during the glass blowing stage of setting the apparatus if blowing is not done through soda lime. In this connection the results of one of the spoiled experiments may be interesting. 27.8 Mg. of the hyponitrite were inserted in the heating column, the latter sealed on to the Sprengel and the apparatus evacuated. On heating no reaction occurred even though the temperature was raised to 450°. The apparatus was left in the same state overnight. Next day about 1 c.c. of gas was formed and the residue gave Na₂CO₃, 0.02663 g. and NaNO₂, 0.0044 g.

C O N C L U S I O N

The indications of these experiments are :

1. Sodium (alkali) hyponitrite is formed, to an appreciable extent, by the reducing action of charcoal on sodium (alkali) nitrite. Its production is low at higher temperatures and under conditions tending to raise the local temperature of the reacting mass.

2. The action of charcoal on alkali nitrites consists of two reactions going on side by side (i) thermal decomposition of the nitrite, accelerated by charcoal, proceeding as :

the reactions (Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 9, 70; *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1943, 20, 261) bringing about auto-oxidation of sodium nitrite being completely eliminated (no nitrate) as the

nitrogen oxides formed in (I) react quantitatively with charcoal as in (II) and (III); (ii) reduction of the nitrite to hyponitrite and production of nitrous oxide from the latter as:

Reaction (VI) occurs at room temperature. This explains why (1) sodium hyponitrite is not obtained from the nitrite by the use of charcoal as a reducing agent, and (2) sodium hyponitrite becomes spoiled on standing by exposure to air; (3) sodium hyponitrite undergoes decomposition at $334\text{--}36^\circ$, probably primarily according to the Diver's equation:

which appears to be followed under the existing conditions, by the reactions attending the auto-oxidation of the produced nitrite as:

This view receives support from the action of charcoal on the hyponitrite.

In view of (3) above it may be argued that in (2) the hyponitrite is the primary product. This, however, cannot be so, for such a case demands the production of larger amounts of carbon dioxide in the earlier stages of the reaction than in subsequent ones. Experiments do not indicate larger proportion of carbon dioxide where the extent of the reaction is small (Table III) than where it is large (Tables I and II).

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